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STUDY ON RIVER BANK SHIFTING BY GIS AND REMOTE SENSING APPROACH OF JAMUNA BRAIDED BELT

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Abstract

Being a braided river, Jamuna has a tendency to deviate the bankline from the original position over the years, causing erosion along the banks. The bank erosion of the river Jamuna has caused suffering for the people living alongside the river bank. The Jamuna river has a tendency of west ward migration. The aim of this study is to find the average erosion rate of the Jamuna river of its both sides and shows that variation of transverse slope of the banks is a possible reason behind the west-ward migration. Bathymetric data of nine stations from (1969-2014) were used in order to find the temporal variation of transverse slope of right bank and left bank channel of Jamuna River. Satellite images were used from longest-running enterprise program Landsat acquired from 1976-2019 and digitalized using Arcmap. The average value of right bank erosion rate was found to be 31.24 m/year towards west, where the left bank erosion rate is 25.18 m/year towards east. This research also shows the increasing trend of average width of the Jamuna river with respect to time. This study will help to access the overall scenario of river shifting and also the bank erosion management of Jamuna River.

Keywords

Braided river, Bank erosion, transverse slope, Landsat, ArcGIS.

1. Introduction

Jamuna, the lowest reach of the Brahmaputra river is marked as braided river because of having several islands composed of bedload and suspended sediments between the channel banks¹. Which indicates the incapacity of the flow to carry sediments resulting sandbars locally known as “chars” across the river. Jamuna has an average discharge of 50000 m³/s², and may exceed 100 000 m³/s in a 100 year flood. Jamuna can get a maximum width of 15 km during the floods (FAP 1, 1992). Jamuna is specially braided because of this amalgamation of variable discharges of water and sediment. A braided river is generally regarded as wide and poorly limned unstable banks which has rapid rates of sideways movement as well as shallow route with multiple channel divisions around alluvial islands. The bank erosion of Jamuna has caused many infrastructures to be damaged permanently and thousands of people have already lost their home (Urmilaz, 2012). They are known as environmental refugees which are one of the most burning issues at this time all over the world (Hoque Mollah and Ferdaush, 2015). This study shows an overall scenario of the erosion and deposition across the banks of Jamuna in recent years and also investigate the relation of transverse gradient with the shifting of bank lines. Transverse gradient is a bathymetric property of river. We have created a hypothesis that transverse gradient may be one of the reasons for the west ward moving tendency of the river which is one of the primary causes of forming braided river (Lane 1957). The study deals with the present condition of average erosion rate of the Jamuna river and both of the banks and increasing trend of average width of the Jamuna river with respect to time. Another objective is to show that variation of transverse slope of both right and left bank is a possible reason behind the west-ward migration.

1.1: Study area

The tectonic movement and the catastrophic flood changed the course of the Brahmaputra and formed a new course now known as Jamuna (Fig 01). Jamuna was originally generated in Himalayas. About 200Km of the total 2900 Km lays in Bangladesh. Which is only 46,644 km² of total 573,500 km² (Baki 2012). Jamuna entered Bangladesh from kurigram then joins with the Ganges taking the name Padma and then the Meghna, finally got discharged in the Bay of Bengal (Ashworth 2000). The latitude-longitude of Brahmaputra-Jamuna River in Bangladesh lays between 23°49'3.38"N, 89°43'6.91"E to 25°57'10.07"N, 89°49'49.40"E. Jamuna has an average

channel width of about 12 km and a valley floor width of 80–90 km. Jamuna also has an average water surface slope is approximately 6.5 cm/km for the lower reach.

Fig 01: The Jamuna river

2. Methodology

Two types of data used in order to perform this study. Images were collected from LANDSAT, the longest running satellite program jointly launched by NASA and USGS. Six LANDSAT images of different year (1976, 1985, 1995, 2005, 2015, and 2019) were used for measuring the shifting rate of the banks of Jamuna river. The scene coordinates in the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection referenced to the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) datum. Jamuna River is cover by two Landsat images. Upper reach of Jamuna is covered from row-128 and path-43 and lower reach from row-128, path-42(Fig 02).

Another set of Bathymetric data from 1969 to 2014 was collected from Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB) for finding the temporal variation of transverse slope near to the right bank and left bank channel of Jamuna River.

Table 1: Details of satellite images

Year	Band	Cell	Bit
1976	4	60*60	8
1985	7	80*80	8
1995	3	30*30	8
2005	7	30*30	8
2015	3	30*30	8
2019	3	30*30	8

After collecting the images, suitable bands were chosen for each time period in order to draw bank line. The bands are chosen based on evident cloud formation during the capture period.

Fig 02: Landsat images of different years

2.1: Bankline Digitization

Satellite images have been digitized by ArcGIS keeping the scale of 1:50000. The bank shifting rate of Jamuna river was determined for different time periods. 1976-1985, 1985-1995, 1995-2005, 2005-2015, 2015-2019 and the respective maps are prepared (Fig 03).

Fig 03: River bank line of respective years

2.2: Determining the Cross Section and Collection of intersection points

Two shape files of different time interval have been overlapped to each other and 16 cross section are taken to calculate the shifting of river bank. Cross-sections were not taken equally. Erosion and deposition occur comparatively much more in the upper section of the Jamuna river than lower section. So, the sections are taken in the upper section more closely than the lower section to calculate the river bank shifting rate. Along the cross section, the change of the river bank both right bank and left bank is calculated for the given time period. Remaining the same cross section, the bank shifting is calculated for all respective time period. The time interval is not same for all the time period. Those are 9 years, 10 years, 10 years, 10 years and 4 years respectively (fig:03). In these time intervals the shifting of river bank is calculated. The values of shifting are being averaged for the all cross sections.

2.3: Channel selection for bathymetric data.

The river was horizontally divided into three reaches (Fig 4). For each reach, three stations were taken. One is in the mid-point of the reach and the other two are at very close near to the starting and ending point of the reaches. The stations are RMJ2, RMJ4, RMJ5 at downstream, RMJ7, RMJ9, RMJ13 at mid-section, RMJ14, RMJ15, RMJ17 at upstream.

Fig 04: Landsat image of 2019 with Old stations of Jamuna River.

2.4: Transverse Slope Determination

The transverse gradients were founded for both right bank channel and left bank channel.

The linear trend line was formatted for each found channel to get a linear equation.

$$Y=mx+c$$

Where, m= gradient of channel

Trend line is known as a line of best fit which is a straight line in channel that shows the general pattern or overall direction of the data. This analytical tool is most often used to show data movements over a period of time or correlation between two variables. Visually, a trend line looks somewhat similar to a line chart, but it doesn't connect the actual data points as a line chart does. A best-fit line shows the general trend in all the data, ignoring statistical errors and minor exceptions.

2.5: Comparison of Transverse Slope

After getting transverse gradient for each channel, a comparison was made between right bank and left bank channel gradient. Which will help to understand the accretion rate into channel as well as the migration tendency.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1: Bank Shifting Rate:

The right bank shifting rate is determined for the respective time period. The positive value indicates the west ward shifting which is erosion and negative values indicates the east ward shifting that is deposition for the right bank. The average values of the all the time period shows that right bank is shifting toward west. The highest value of erosion is 358.375 m followed in the time period 1976-1985. And the lowest value is 55.625 m for time period 2015-2019

The left bank shifting rate is determined for the respective time period (Table 2). The positive value indicates the east ward shifting which is deposition and negative values indicates the west ward shifting that is erosion for the right bank. The average values of the all-time period show that left bank is shifting toward east. The highest value of erosion is -828.88 m followed in the time period 1976-1985. And the lowest value is -137.133 m for time period 2015-2019. Deposition occurred in the left bank for time period 2005-2015 which is 439.5 m.

Table 2: Bank shifting rate

Cross section	Year									
	1976-1985	1985-1995	1995-2005	2005-2015	2015-2019	1976-1985	1985-1995	1995-2005	2005-2015	2015-2019
	Right Bank					Left Bank				
1	20	186	685	68	194	0	61	-91	114	-132
2	245	-993	842	424	251	2	158	43	76	-86
3	1051	588	241	509	31	-804	1041	-662	58	-131
4	1338	313	-149	963	-1106	-580	-3781	-165	-360	-228
5	120	662	-55	-179	571	-889	-2	-1295	92	-298
6	-77	490	176	398	-117	1341	-554	1083	306	-49
7	610	-953	236	1166	399	-1693	398	109	-810	-6
8	-3	721	86	339	-24	-1358	-2071	-2029	129	-214
9	163	726	358	31	278	-383	3136	359	72	-44
10	-318	1832	958	1490	119	-863	549	-639	4115	104
11	1150	1514	982	453	-38	-523	1458	2885	1097	320
12	397	1623	1660	1402	403	-1793	890	-444	-131	-120
13	-202	1216	-2477	-3494	-33	-945	-1968	-168	439	-35
14	1783	-812	99	450	656	-2797	1148	-2773	2489	-135
15	-426	292	508	313	-124	-1843	-5041	1539	-1028	-402
16	-117	421	-39	109	-570	-134	278	88	374	-93
Average	358.375	489.125	256.9375	277.625	55.625	-828.8	-268.8	-166.3	439.5	-137.133

3.2: Shifting rate

Fig 05: Shifting rate of right bank and left bank

Average shifting of right bank=31.236 m/year Average shifting of left bank=-25.19 m/year It is concluded that the average shifting rate of right bank is more than left bank.

Fig 06: The change of bank line between 1976-2019

3.3 Average Width

Table 3.3: Average River width.

The average width of the Jamuna River is calculated and plotted year-wise (Fig 07). The average width of the Jamuna River was 9 km in 1976 and now the average width is 11.56 km. The width is found growing except the time period of 2005-2015. This study concludes that the width of river is increasing day by day.

Fig 07: Graphical representation of river width.

Comparison of transverse slope

Fig 08: Temporal Variation of Transverse Gradient

After plotting the average data for each available year, the plot shows that the Right Bank channel gradients are larger than the Left Bank channel gradients for almost every year except 1981 (Fig 08). This could be one of the factors of west ward migration of Jamuna River. The trend line shows a constant gap between the year-wise gradient of right bank and the left bank which could be the reason behind the comparatively larger shifting rate of right bank.

4. Conclusion

This study has been carried out by six satellite images of Landsat collected between 1976-2019 and bathymetric data collected from Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB). To quantify the present tendency of west ward migration of Jamuna River we have find out the bank shifting rate both right bank and left bank as well as the temporal variation of lateral geometric properties. This study reveals that Jamuna River is highly unstable river. We have determined the erosion rate for the right bank. The erosion rate is maximum for time period 1985-1995, which is 48.9 m/yr. The lowest rate of erosion is 14 m/yr in 2015-2019. The average value of right bank shifting rate is 31.236 m/yr which is in west ward direction. We also determined the shifting rate for left bank. The erosion rate is maximum for time period 1976-1985 which is 90.09 m/yr. The lowest rate of erosion is 16.625 m/yr in 1995-2005. The average value of left bank shifting rate is -25.18 m/yr. The average width of was found 9 km in 1976 and 11.56 km in 2019. We have found a constant gap between transverse gradient of right bank and left bank which concludes the fact that right bank is steeper than the left bank which could be the possible reason behind the west ward migration tendency of Jamuna. There are many investigations carried out to find the possible reason behind the increasing erosion rate, transverse slope may be another reason for bank shifting.

5. Acknowledgement

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